

Multimodal Reading Model for a Rural Elementary School

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ABSTRACT

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This study intends to develop a multimodal learning model to assist teachers in addressing issues related to students' poor reading performance in a rural elementary school in the Province of Sorsogon, Philippines. The study used the qualitative case study method to achieve its objectives. Data were acquired through document reviews, individual interviews, and focus group discussions with the informants purposefully selected for the study. Results showed that for the school year 2023 to 2024, out of 166 learners, four pupils belonged to the description of meeting expectations; 53 belonged to full intervention; 55 belonged to moderate intervention; and 54 belonged to light intervention. Meanwhile, for the school year 2022 to 2023, out of 202 learners, 30 pupils belonged to the description of meeting expectations; 16 belonged to full intervention; 104 belonged to moderate intervention; and 52 belonged to light intervention. Given this reading performance, this study proposes a multimodal reading model for a rural elementary school. The goal is to enhance the reading proficiency of the pupils by supporting reading teachers who use multimodal reading models to teach non-readers. The teachers' feedback on using multimodal reading tools revealed both their positive and challenging experiences. Future studies may aim to develop, implement, and evaluate advanced multimodal reading technologies used in autonomous cooperative learning and reading intervention programs and activities.

KEYWORDS:

multimodal reading model, reading performance, reading program

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education (DepEd) has planned for using information and communication technologies (ICT) in schools. DepEd aims to create an ICT-enabled education system that uses technology to turn students into digital natives who are value-centered, creative, and responsible citizens. The goal of using technology in all learning areas is to get students more involved in the teaching and learning process and to help them learn more and get better at what they already know. So, a teacher must be able to read, write, and use more than one medium to teach. To reach this objective, teachers need to be given the tools they need to meet the DepEd ICT Competency Standard.

DepEd also wants to change education through the its computerization program, which was introduced through DepEd Order No. 78, s. 2010. The goal of the computerization program is to give secondary schools

computer laboratory packages, incorporate ICT into the school system, and improve the ICT literacy of students, teachers, and school heads. This program was made because it was said that Filipino students had done very poorly on several tests, raising worries about how well the K–12 program was working. Problems found include an overloaded curriculum, too many teaching demands in too little time, and an overall too heavy academic load for both teachers and students, which made it harder to learn basic skills like reading and simple math. Because of this, teachers need to come up with useful learning activities that use different ways to teach.

Recently, DepEd introduced the MATATAG curriculum on January 30, 2023. This method tackles educational obstacles by emphasizing reading and mathematics. MATATAG will focus on creating a curriculum that is pertinent to developing skilled and employable individuals, enhancing basic education resources and services, fostering student welfare, inclusive education, and a conducive learning atmosphere, and empowering teachers to improve their teaching methods. The MATATAG curriculum focuses on reading, numeracy, and socio-emotional development for pupils in kindergarten through grade 3,

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streamlining the K-12 curriculum. DepEd also introduced Project SMILE to create a secure and nurturing educational setting in all schools. It presupposes that teachers who are compassionate and nurturing may offer the most optimal and secure learning setting. Enthusiastic and committed teachers create a delightful atmosphere in classrooms. You can watch movies, play games, listen to music, and engage in other activities.

The use of multimodal tools is essential in creating a welcoming and nurturing atmosphere that aligns with active pedagogy and learner-centered approaches. Multimodality is the integration of two or more modalities, including written language, spoken language, visual, audio, gestural, and spatial meaning. The use of multimodal literacy to ready students for the evolving communication landscape is gaining recognition and being included in many literacy curricula worldwide. The problem persists for teachers in designing for students' multimodal literacy learning in the classroom. Challenges involve the insufficient ICT skills for using multimodal tools and the lack of suitable ICT tools for instructors to teach reading (Ganapathy & Seetharam, 2016). Teachers must acquire abilities in utilizing digital technologies, namely computers, to fully engage with the current curriculum. They need to be proficient in both basic and advanced computer skills.

Teachers in rural places face challenges in using a multimodal approach to learning due to limited internet connectivity, which hinders their ability to acquire information that could enhance students' learning results. This instance presents substantial issues with student participation, including limited access to costly tools and insufficient time to adjust to new learning approaches. Thus, it is essential to address these concerns while transitioning to a more sustainable approach to engaging with emerging technologies (Julinar, 2019). Existing issues hindered the success of implementing multimodal learning in school. Challenges include inadequate teacher training in utilizing technology tools, hindering work performance, limited access to equipment, frequent technical issues, and insufficient immediate technical and administrative assistance. These issues significantly impact the academic performance of ICT teachers and students (Azimzadeh et al., 2021).

In the case of a rural elementary school in Castilla, Sorsogon which is under the jurisdiction of Castilla South District, Province of Sorsogon, Region V, Philippines, the school has internet access, enabling teachers and learners to use technological tools in the teaching and learning process. Of the 177 students enrolled in the school for the academic year 2023 to 2024, there are 94 males and 83 females. Teachers also know about the school facilities and equipment they use to teach students. They all utilized technology teaching tools to enhance their lessons but faced challenges due to insufficient school facilities and equipment, which had a significant impact on the students' performance. Therefore, this research might be an important endeavor as this

exploratory research helped to tackle the challenges faced by the reading teachers while employing multimodal learning resources and the expectation for them to create and utilize these materials. Addressing the current difficulties and sharing study findings can promote improvements in administrative strategies and support for reading teachers, benefiting their students.

Related Literature

Teachers who want to make a difference in learning must effectively teach learners with good instructional resources for the realization of daily lesson objectives (Barber et al., 2014; Ferguson et al., 2019; Christ et al., 2019; Bus et al., 2019; and Arante et al., 2020). Digital learning technologies are used to enhance learners' abilities in innovation, leadership, interdisciplinary collaboration, emotional intelligence, critical thinking, and problem-solving in a participatory setting. Student learning is enhanced using various interactive tools and resources, as opposed to relying solely on text.

Teachers need to develop innovative and meaningful instructional strategies and tools that may enhance learning outcomes and assist pupils and teachers in overcoming learning obstacles (Reantaso, & Digo, 2022; Mostera, & Digo, 2023). Tope (2021) created and employed multimedia learning materials and methods to improve learning. However, Magnusson & Godhe (2019) revealed that the application of multimodality in educational settings is hampered by several issues, including the fact that multimodality has not been fully adopted by most English curricula, including English as a second language, and educational contexts due to a scarcity of knowledge on how teachers might incorporate multimodality into their present curriculum. Educational contexts and practices discourage the use of multimodality, and a lack of explicit awareness and understanding of the concept of multimodality has also posed a challenge to the implementation of multimodality. These were backed up by the studies of Julinar (2019) and Rodchu, Lamerias, and Anoda (2022) who showed in their studies about the experiences of teachers in using multimodal in the teaching-learning process that there were several problems encountered by educators with the use of multimodal learning delivery, which is also the main concern of the present study.

Jiang and Gao (2020), Ioannou et al. (2022), Ally et al. (2022), Nouri (2019); Chen and Jamiat (2023) and Katz et al. (2021) observed that the inclusion of multimodal digital composition tasks contributed to the development of digital empathy amongst learners and helped to increase their motivation and confidence in expressing themselves in English. Likewise, the teacher's multimodal pedagogies in designing opportunities for students' multimodal composing were well-received by the students, who appreciated the range of meaning-making options. It enables faculty members to reach more diverse student bodies because it equips them with more tools to tailor learning to meet a variety of needs

with proper training on its usage. Its positive effects were strengthened by the study of Azimzadeh et al. (2021), Marantila (2021), Chen (2021), Ganapathy and Seetharam (2016) revealed that using multimodal approaches and learning resources greatly improves reading skills and the academic performance of students. Further, Buai (2021), Cartwright et al. (2016), Zhou and Yadav (2017); Wong and Neuman (2019) stressed the effects of motivation on students' comprehension of reading texts. It has a significant influence on their reading behavior and ability, and promoted motivation may also positively influence students' reading fluency and reading skills. Just like the present undertaking, which will focus on the use of multimodal learning delivery models or resources as motivation to make the teaching-learning process effective.

Most studies focused on the impact of multimodal learning methodologies on students' academic performance. Some individuals concentrated on enhancing the academic achievement of students by examining the usability of Google apps and other digital resources. Some studied the efficacy of multimodal microlearning for in-service teachers, problem-based learning in multimodal environments, learners' technology adoption experiences, and teachers' competence in delivering learning. Others concentrated on the issues and difficulties faced by teachers when using multimodal learning methods and materials, all of which are relevant to the current project. Hence, this study was conducted to explore teachers' experiences with using a multimodal learning delivery strategy at a rural elementary school in Castilla South District, Sorsogon Philippines. The goal was to create multimodal learning resources to enhance students' reading performance. This is the gap that the current project has attempted to close.

Objectives

This study intends to develop a multimodal reading model to assist reading teachers in addressing issues related to students' poor reading performance. Moreover, this paper investigated teachers' experiences and feedback on implementing the proposed multimodal reading tools.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design.

The researcher used a descriptive case study design to investigate the informants' experiences with the multimodal reading model. This design is the suitable for this study as it focuses on describing teachers' experiences on using the multimodal paradigm in teaching reading.

The Informants.

The informants consisted of six elementary teachers from a rural school in Castilla South District, Sorsogon, Philippines. Out of the six selected teacher participants, two are male and four are female. The informants were selected based on the following criteria: employed in the locale of the study, reading teachers, willing to take part in the interview and workshops, and willing to sign the informed consent form

to voluntarily participate in this study. The informants' names were withheld to safeguard their identities, in line with ethical research practices.

The Instrument.

The primary tool used in this study was a researcher-developed interview guide with open-ended questions. It was utilized for interviewing the teachers chosen as informants for the study. During the interview, additional questions were asked to participants to gather more data and delve deeper into teachers' experiences with the creation and use of multimodal learning tools.

Data Collection Procedures.

The researcher requested data on the outcomes of the National Achievement Test (NAT) and of the Comprehensive Rapid Learning Assessment (CRLA) over the past two years by sending a communication letter to the school's CRLA coordinator. The primary goal was to assess the reading proficiency of students. Interviews and focus group discussions were utilized to create a plan and design suitable instructional multimodal learning delivery. This strategy enables researchers to obtain detailed data related to the materials that must be created based on learners' reading performance.

Researchers conducted individual interviews with teachers to collect data on their feedback regarding the use of the multimodal reading delivery method. The researcher reached out to the informants using a cellphone number provided by the respondents in the consent letter. Some individuals are contacted by Messenger to arrange a specific time and day for the interview. Teachers were allowed to select the interview location to ensure they were at ease when providing information and discussing the topic. Each participant had one hour to answer the questions during the in-person interview. During the interview, participants were asked follow-up questions to enable the researchers to delve deeper into the experience of the informants on the multimodal reading model. This assisted the researcher in collecting more comprehensive and detailed data on teachers' experiences, as well as the user-friendliness and effectiveness of materials.

In addition, the researchers conducted focus group discussions and interviews to enhance the data and develop reading delivery mechanisms. It enabled researchers to gather information and insights regarding the advancement of materials designed to cater to the needs of learners, especially in enhancing their reading skills.

Data Analysis Procedure.

Audio recordings from the cell phone during the interview and focused group discussions were transcribed. The transcribed data were analyzed using coding to organize the results and create themes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the reading performance of , the proposed multimodal reading model, and the feedback from reading teachers.

1. Reading Performance of the Rural Elementary School

Table 1 shows that in the reading performance of the elementary school for the school year 2023 to 2024, out of 166 primary learners, only four pupils belonged to the description of “meeting expectations”; 53 belonged to “full intervention”; 55 belonged to “moderate intervention”; and 54 belonged to “light intervention”. Moreover, for the school year 2022 to 2023, out of 202 learners, only 30 primary pupils belonged to the description of “meeting expectations”; 16 belonged to “full intervention”; 104 belonged to “moderate intervention”, and 52 belonged to “light intervention”.

Table 1. Reading Performance of the Rural Elementary School

Reading Performance	SY 2023-2024	SY 2022-2023
Full Intervention	53	16
Moderate Intervention	55	104
Light Intervention	54	52
Meet Expectations	4	30
Total	166	202

The reading performance of the rural elementary school is representative of the reading performance in the region where it belongs. For example, in Region V, data show that 36.5% of the learners are full refreshers, 11% are moderate refreshers, 19.13% are light refreshers, and only 33.37% are grade-ready, as revealed in the conduct of the CRLA in Region V, Philippines. Likewise, as revealed in the NAT results during the past years, there is an existing problem with the reading comprehension of pupils. The NAT result for the school year 2013 to 2014 showed that Sorsogon City ranked last among the 13 divisions in the Bicol Region, with 47.03% NAT mean percentage score (MPS) results for the division, while Sorsogon Province ranked sixth with a 58.04 MPS. Hence, evidence-based reading intervention is needed to address the problems of education along with the dismal results in reading (Tambyraja, & Schmitt, 2020).

In the case of the rural elementary school. teachers may provide learners with a conducive reading atmosphere and must continue conducting reading remediation to make all learners readers (Phala, & Hugo, 2022). Teachers must carry out a comprehensive reading program, develop the

skills they lack, and track progress to ensure that everyone in the class improves steadily in their abilities. Moreover, teachers may continue developing instructional reading materials to meet the needs of learners and make teaching reading efficient and effective. It may also be possible to implement technological tools in the classroom because of internet connectivity in the school. Reading teachers may also continue to measure and assess pupils’ performance as a basis for planning, designing, and using reading instruction tools and programs to improve the overall school’s reading performance. Hence, this study believes that reading teachers may design and implement an innovative multimodal reading model that can effectively bring positive changes in the reading proficiency of learners.

2. Multimodal Reading Model for Readers and Reading Teachers

This study developed a multimodal reading model to make all primary pupils a reader. This multimodal reading model aims to improve the reading performance of non-readers in elementary schools. Specifically, this model aims to assist teachers in the use of the multimodal reading model in teaching non-readers, ensure the implementation of reading programs using the developed multimodal reading tools, and enhance the use of technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge of teachers in using multimodal reading tools. This multimodal reading model is composed of three domains namely: Technological pedagogical, and content knowledge on the use of multimodal reading tools. Moreover, various multimodal reading tools and technologies are identified for each domain.

Technological knowledge is understanding how technology is utilized to engage all learners as active creators and consumers. The teacher may use technology like PowerPoint, interactive games, worksheets, projectors, DVDs, CDs, and computers for the reading intervention which are suitable for addressing reading difficulties aids in learning. This information pertains to the theory of technology, which discusses the wide-ranging effects of technology on education, especially in influencing students’ learning (Spacey, 2020). Directly using multimodal reading tools helps students achieve the program’s purpose. Informants indicated that they create multimedia learning resources to enhance students’ reading skills, even in the absence of adequate school facilities and technology. However, inadequate equipment or connectivity hindered the integration of electronic tools in the classroom. Participants also replied that enhancing training on technical instruments, such as computers and ICT tools, is necessary to facilitate teachers in utilizing various technology advancements when teaching digitally-native learners.

Figure 1: Multimodal Reading Model

Koehler et al. (2014) highlights the significance of pedagogical knowledge in utilizing multimodal learning tools. It emphasizes the impact of using a specific technology on teaching and learning. The researcher has developed pedagogical methods leveraging multimodal learning delivery technologies such as playing games, using video and music, listening to a song, reading words and stories in a PowerPoint, and visual representation. Moreover, these teaching methods are combined with multimodal reading aids in this program. These notions are based on Bruner's thesis from 1961, suggesting that educators with pedagogical expertise in technology create a setting that encourages learners to actively engage in the learning process, enabling students to use their senses to comprehend concepts, information, and skills. Teachers can employ various tactics and activities to enhance the flexibility, accessibility, interactivity, and engagement of lessons based on comments from teachers regarding the use of multimodal learning resources. Bansong and Poopatwiboon (2023) proposed that teaching and learning should be reoriented towards multimodal pedagogical techniques to achieve better learning outcomes, increase motivation to learn, accommodate different learning styles, and enhance the students' experience.

Content knowledge refers to the teachers' comprehension of the material or lesson they are teaching students in reading instruction. Teachers must master various topics in language and literacy domains to effectively deliver lessons using multimodal reading tools for high-quality teaching and learning. These topics include oral language, phonological awareness, book and print knowledge, alphabet knowledge, phonics and word recognition, fluency, spelling, writing and composition, grammar awareness and structure, vocabulary development, reading comprehension, and listening comprehension. The concepts emphasize the principle of constructivism, which posits that competencies like attitudes, knowledge, and abilities cannot be imparted but must be actively obtained by the learner. The study found a connection between teachers' content expertise, the substance of the lesson, and the use of multimodal learning aids to improve teaching and learning results. Therefore, it was suggested that teachers receive ongoing training in utilizing multi-modal learning methods, fostering teacher-student interaction, mastering subject matter, providing instruction, promoting active and personalized learning, conducting learning assessments, and ensuring inclusion to maintain their competence.

Through a Google link, both readers and learners can access the multimodal reading tools. PowerPoint

presentations, worksheets, and audio clips to assist teachers and pupils in using the multi-modal learning delivery model are available. The link also includes DepEd TV episodes, the Bikol Kotobee App, #LearnSmart_eStorytelling Sessions, and other games, videos, and activity sheets prepared by teachers for instruction purposes. Students are expected to finish one lesson a day with the help of teachers and parents, with remedial reading conducted daily. However, teachers must download essential technological apps like Kotobee Reader, Windows Media Player, MP3, MP4, and Microsoft PowerPoint for the tools to function correctly. Students can use the link to follow the teachings and directions provided by PowerPoint, with activity sheets for follow-up tasks provided by teachers. The link also contains folders organized per lesson, including applications, audio, PowerPoint presentations, and activity sheets. These can be brought home for follow-up and remedial reading.

3. Teachers' Feedback on the Utilization of the Multimodal Reading Model

The feedback of the teachers on the use of multimodal reading tools is divided into two: themes which are: Positive experiences and negative experiences of informants in terms of ease of use of multimodal reading tool. Meanwhile along its usability, these were divided into three sub-themes which are: multi-modal reading tool is engaging, multi-modal reading tool is challenging, and multi-modal reading tool is useful.

Positive experiences on the use of the multimodal reading tools. Informants have positive experiences with the ease of use of the multi-modal reading tool, as indicated by their statements. For example, Informant 3 said that the “the material is suitable for the kids' age group and skill level, making it easier to use throughout the reading session. The tool is user-friendly as it allows you to quickly discern its alignment with learning objectives and its potential impact on student outcomes. Likewise, Informant 1 relayed that the “reading materials are user-friendly and adaptable for teachers, students, and parents. The package includes comprehensive directions, resources, exercises, tests, and answers.”

These teachers' comments may suggest that using instructional and technology resources, including multi-modal learning delivery, significantly enhances the effectiveness of the teaching-learning process. It may also enhance the flexibility, accessibility, interactivity, and engagement of lessons for both teachers and learners. Likewise, the participants' reactions are akin to those in a study by Ganapathy and Seetharam (2016) that investigated the impact of multimodal teaching and learning methods on literacy and meaning-making among 15 students at a private school in Penang, Malaysia. The results showed that ESL teaching and learning should be redirected towards multimodal pedagogical techniques to enhance students' learning outcomes. The multimodal approaches included in teaching and learning can enhance students' autonomy in

learning, boost motivation to learn, and accommodate different learning styles.

This finding of this study like Julinar's (2019) research report, which revealed that teachers hold favorable views on using multimodality in their teaching practices. They incorporated it as a valuable tool for teaching using various terminologies and methods. The school's available facilities are believed to necessitate inventiveness in instructing young learners. Schools and teachers are accountable for fostering students' motivation, catering to their specific learning needs, and acquainting them with diverse learning methods. Sharples (2016) emphasized that digital learning multi-modal technologies enhance learners' abilities in innovation, leadership, interdisciplinary collaboration, emotional intelligence, critical thinking, and collective problem-solving in a participatory setting. It supports various teaching and training approaches, educational goals, evaluation techniques, and feedback systems to improve students' learning experience. Sankey et al. (2010) suggests that utilizing multimodal technological tools can cater to the varied requirements of extensive student populations by incorporating visual, auditory, reading/writing, and kinesthetic components. This approach immerses students in interactive learning settings, fostering a sense of connection with both their peers and the educational material.

Moreover, the usability of multi-modal reading tools was discussed by informants, highlighting three sub-themes: engaging, difficult, and useful.

The multi-modal reading tool is engaging. The informants provided views that the multimodal reading tools are engaging. For example, Informant 5 said that “the use of this material improves the learning process and boosts participation among students, and reading sessions become more dynamic, fostering an interactive, enjoyable, and efficient learning environment. Similarly, Informant 3 shared that “it is an excellent tool for enhancing student engagement, motivation, and knowledge retention, leading to more inclusive and engaging learning experiences.”

These results demonstrate how engaging multi-modal reading tools are in the delivery methods to improve the teaching-learning process. The use of the interactive learning resources in the class motivated learners to become more interactive in their learning. The researcher's prepared materials led to greater student participation and strong motivation in class. Chen and Jamiat (2023) also did an investigation and built an interactive multimodal application based on the cognitive-affective theory of learning with media interactively and found out that that students' intrinsic motivation and comprehension were enhanced by using the multi-modal tools. Jiang and Gao (2020) supported the findings by stating that incorporating multimodal digital composition tasks enhanced learners' digital empathy, motivation, and confidence in self-expression. Choi and Yi (2016) suggest that English instructors should receive clear

instruction on how to teach reading comprehension utilizing multimodality throughout both preservice and in-service training. Teachers should consistently assess their teaching methods and seek strategies to enhance any areas of deficiency. Consequently, learners will develop a profound awareness of the instructional strategies for multimodal reading comprehension, along with the elements that facilitate or hinder multimodal teaching in classrooms. In addition, the scenarios align with Dopson's (2023) concept that engaging learners can be achieved through the utilization of multi-modal learning resources. Utilizing several approaches allows learners to comprehend and remember knowledge regardless of their learning styles, therefore promoting engagement throughout the entire class.

The multi-modal reading tool is easy to use.

Teachers found using the learning tool tough based on the replies from the informants. Informant 4 shared that “using multimodal learning technologies positively impacts teaching, especially in catering to learners' requirements. Students demonstrated stronger reading skills, improved comprehension, and increased creativity. Students easily find the solution to the question or clue that I provide by utilizing multimodal learning resources such as visuals, body movement, and noises.” Because it is easy to use, students may actively engage in the session, leading to improved learning outcomes and the development of their skills and knowledge. Nouri (2019) also showed that using multimodal approaches helps teachers cater to a wider range of student needs by providing them with various tools for personalized learning. Easy to use multimodal technologies therefore may enhance personalized and inclusive engagement between students and instructors. Teachers and students can engage in a wider range of activities and connect on multiple levels.

Furthermore, the findings relate to Choi and Yi's (2021) research on the utilization and efficacy of multimodal teaching in the field of English language instruction where they showed that multimodal education had an impact on students' motivation, productive skills, reading skills, and learning autonomy. Likewise, Barber et al. (2014) highlighted that incorporating easy to use multimedia learning tools into various learning methods promotes a more adaptable learning strategy focused on inquiry and knowledge retrieval. Hence, student learning is enhanced by utilizing a variety of interactive tools and resources, as opposed to relying just on text-based materials. Katz et al. (2021) noted that students learn more profoundly through multimodal learning, which combines several forms of representation (text, video, audio, and visuals), compared to just words. This holds for both in-person and online classes.

The multimodal reading tool enhances the effectiveness of the reading teacher. Informants reported that the generated learning materials are beneficial in terms of enhancing the effectiveness of the reading teachers. According to Informant 5, “from my experience with this educational tool, it indeed simplifies classroom delivery,

particularly in reading interventions, even with a diverse student population resulting to more effective learning sessions.” The informants suggest that utilizing multi-modal learning delivery tools “reduces the workload for teachers when instructing students in reading, particularly during reading intervention programs (I3, I2). These tools offer teachers a chance to enhance their teaching methods to accommodate the varying needs of their students. Consequently, the use of multi-modal learning delivery tools makes it simpler and more effective for teachers to conduct remedial reading lessons (Tope, 2021). Moreover, Lee-Cultura (2017) highlights the benefits of incorporating technological tools, such as multi-modal learning tools, in education to enhance the quality of instruction. Utilizing technology allows for efficient project management and facilitates effective communication between teachers and students, leading to improved learning outcomes. To cater to the diverse learning styles of students in school settings, teachers should utilize multiple multimodal learning tools to create a comprehensive educational experience, ultimately promoting academic success for all students (Prodigy, 2023).

Negative experiences on the use of the multimodal reading tools. Informants had negative experiences with the usability of multi-modal reading tools based on the reading teachers' comments, indicating issues faced by teachers. Informant 6 mentioned that “using multimodal learning tools were technological issues, resource selection, and assuring accessibility for all students. To overcome those obstacles, it is essential to offer training and assistance to teachers, work together with colleagues, and utilize trustworthy platforms and resources.” Moreover, informant 4 said that she “struggled using this multi-modal tool because of my limited computer skills and difficulty connecting it to a PowerPoint presentation. I rely on my co-teachers for help. However, I find it easy to use modules while teaching reading.” Similarly, Informant 3 found out that “the process of connecting devices such as laptops and projectors before teaching can be time-consuming.”

These responses revealed that although multi-modal learning tools had negative experiences due to issues with their use and manipulation. This highlights the need to enhance training on utilizing technological tools like computers and ICT to facilitate the integration of various technological advancements in teaching digitally-native students. The results align with Magnusson and Godhe's (2019) study, which identified obstacles in utilizing multi-modal learning tools, including a lack of information on integrating multimodality into current curricula by teachers and a limited understanding of its use.

Domínguez and Bobkina, (2021) reported that while there are benefits to using multimodal classroom approaches for teaching and learning, studies have shown challenges in implementing multimodal pedagogies. These challenges include teachers' willingness to use multimodality and their preparedness to teach multimodal literacy. In the same way,

Méndez et al. (2018) found out that teacher training on the use of technology contributes the most to the existence of digital inequality and digital inclusivity among students. The higher levels of culture for professional development among teachers at school increased levels of digital competence among students. That is why it is important that training for teachers on the utilization of multi-modal technologies be strengthened since the success of multimodality is largely dependent on the teachers' ability to seamlessly manipulate content, pedagogy, technology, and other modes to bring out a whole new experience of learning. As suggested by Boelens et al. (2017), teachers must be able to create fresh and purposeful educational techniques and choices that not only improve learning results but also help students overcome challenges of blended learning. As such, developing the capability of teachers to use technology through training should be strengthened to maximize the appropriate use of technology in the classroom and to create a positive effect on students' attitudes and performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher drew the following conclusions from the findings of the study. The majority of students at Cogon Elementary School are part of the complete intervention program, indicating the need for a remedial reading intervention to improve their reading skills. A multimodal reading model was created to help teachers utilize several reading aids to enhance learners' reading skills. Teachers have both positive and negative feedback regarding the effectiveness and user-friendliness of multi-modal learning delivery materials. Despite its convenience, multimodal material is also entertaining, valuable, and challenging. Finally, given the results and the conclusions reached, teachers may need to dedicate time and effort to develop, implement, and evaluate advanced multimodal reading technologies that may be used in autonomous cooperative learning and reading intervention programs and activities. The advanced multimodal reading model can be used to construct a reading intervention program along with the developed multimodal reading tools from this study.

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